

The appearance of physical exercises in the territory of our country in ancient times

Kurbanov Djurabek Ismatovich

Bukhara State University

d.i.kurbanov@buxdu.uz

Annotation. *Avitsenna gave the form and content of the exercise and its essence in the complex of measures for hygiene, health improvement and treatment of the patient. Avitsenna was the first to create a doctrine, that is, a classification of physical exercises, which determined when and in what order each person should practice. According to Avitsenna, "the main measure of health is physical fitness."*

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Every social system is directly related to the future, the future of humanity, the standard of living of people, the development of science and culture. The development of science and culture depends on the level of educational work. This philosophical belief is a social law of state importance.

Therefore, after independence in our country, "Education and upbringing has been identified as a priority in the field of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan." [6]

One of the urgent tasks facing our society and state is to take care of people, to bring up and bring up the younger generation as a mature person, modern, educated, highly spiritual, strong-willed, strong-willed person. As the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted, the most important task before us now is "... - to put them at the center of educational work, to raise them to a new level, to educate our young generation to be mature thinkers with independent thinking in all respects. [2. 4 p] It is known that the upbringing of young people is the product of our national traditions, customs, love for our immortal heritage, the spirit of devotion to them, the work we do for each of us. In the current era of globalization, it is important to form immunity against foreign ideas, to use the spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, to improve the methods of ideological education, which are widely used today, to form a culture of effective use of the Internet. The faith of the people and its spirit have such a powerful influence that it creates the basis for creative work of every sane person, for the honesty of his profession.

The Uzbek people have such a divine blessing, they have their own national faith. We can see this in the image of great people, thinkers. Because the spirit of the

people and the faith in it are expressed by the most advanced representatives of the nation, the thinkers.

The work of Zakhridin Muhammad Babur, the sultan of the poetry garden, the great thinker and statesman, which is an expression of the potential and opportunity in the psyche of our people, is also an immortal example of the people's faith. We are always proud of the great name of the thinker, the immortality of his creative heritage, the fact that his artistic genius knows no bounds of time and space. In the words of our first President Islam Karimov: "If we call this great man a saint, he is a saint of saints, a thinker, a thinker of thinkers, a poet, a sultan of poets." [1. 7 p]

From the first days of independence of Uzbekistan, the task was to highlight the history of the country and reveal all the realities. It is known that our country is famous for its great scientists, generals and statesmen who have made an invaluable contribution to world culture. In the development of national culture, Uzbekistan has long been one of the leading cultural centers in the history of mankind among the countries of the world, the countries of Central Asia, due to its unique features, geographical and natural amenities.

Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037). One of the great scientists of world medicine, Avitsenna was a sage well versed in philosophy, literature, music and many other fields. The scientific and pedagogical heritage of Avitsenna is enormous. Abu Ali ibn Sina's most famous work is *The Laws of Medicine*, which is of particular importance. This work was first translated into Uzbek, translated into other languages in 1153, and then repeatedly reprinted (1956, 1980, 1993). On the initiative of the government and public organizations of the republic, in 1980 a large scientific conference was held in Bukhara on the occasion of the 1000th anniversary of the birth of Abu Ali ibn Sina. It is noted that in the works of Avitsenna much attention was paid to education and physical education. More than 30 medical works of the thinker-scientist have survived to this day. The author's works highlight the essence of physical education, advanced ideas about physical exercises and the content of practical classes.

Avitsenna gave the form and content of the exercise and its essence in the complex of measures for hygiene, health improvement and treatment of the patient. Avitsenna was the first to create a doctrine, that is, a classification of physical exercises, which determined when and in what order each person should practice. According to Avitsenna, "the main measure of health is physical fitness."

The first part of the book "*Laws of Medicine*" is devoted to the protection and development of human health. The book scientifically describes the human body and its organs, the anatomical structures that take place during the formation and development of a person, the state of physiological and mental processes, the causes of diseases. [5. 47 p]

In his writings, the advice of Avitsenna is very important that the exercises should be performed in different forms and styles depending on the age, gender, health, well-being and illness of a person. Based on the work and experience of Avitsenna, he gave specific instructions on how a person should respond to physical exercise in childhood, adolescence, youth and old age. This legacy of scientific and pedagogical education has made a significant contribution to the development of physical culture of the peoples of the world.

Avitsenna described "physical training as a voluntary action that makes one breathe deeply and consistently." According to Avitsenna, a person who does not exercise suffers from severe pain (constriction of the limbs) because his limbs become weak as a result of inactivity. He divided the types of physical education into two main groups:

1) actions of a person in the course of work;

2) special physical education classes. When the great scientist spoke about physical training, he meant mainly special physical education classes. There are many types of exercises and they are divided into fast, thin, easy, strong and weak groups.

Ibn Sina included shooting, boxing, fast walking, javelin throwing, hanging, jumping on one leg, fencing, javelin throwing and horseback riding as fast-acting types of physical training. The thin and light types include jumping rope, swinging or lying on a swing, boating, and other activities. A strong form of physical training includes exercises such as wrestling with one's own shadow, playing ball with large and small balls, wrestling, lifting stones, pulling a galloping horse off the leash.

According to Avitsenna, during physical training, fast and sharp movements are performed, alternating with light ones, and certain movements are not performed for a long time. In the treatment of various ailments, he recommended the use of spiritual nutrition, ways of enjoyment, that is, the use of various factors, such as travel, travel, boating, enjoying natural scenery.

According to the scientist, the massage will be rough or light. Rough massage is performed with a rough cloth. Light massage is done with a light cloth. Massage is mainly done to tighten weakened limbs, tighten soft ones, soften roughness and soften hard ones. Physical massage is also taught here: 1) preparatory massage; 2) post-workout massage. The significance of massage in accelerating the work of the circulatory system, improving breathing, and the proper functioning of the digestive organs is fully reflected in the scientific and practical education of the scientist. Avitsenna considered rest, sleep and proper nutrition to be the most important factors in maintaining health. One of the most important aspects of Avitsennas teachings on physical education is wrestling. There are also several types of wrestling. One of them is for each of the two wrestlers to grab their opponent by the belt while the wrestler takes action to get rid of his opponent. The other tries not to let go. Another

type: one of the two wrestlers hugs the other with both arms and pulls him to the side, during which time the first wrestler must pass under his right arm, (wrestlers) sometimes straighten their legs, and sometimes bend (types of wrestling) include repeating a chest strike, bending over another person's neck, confusing each other's legs with one's own, playing or tearing the other's leg with the legs, using wrestlers. [6. 74 p]

Avitsenna gave concrete examples of the fact that special efforts are made to each part of the body to improve the health of a person through physical training and bring it to perfection. It combines the movements of the arms and legs with the natural movements of the chest and respiratory organs, as well as all other organs. He performed exercises such as moving all the organs of the vocal cords, making loud noises, sticking out the tongue, stretching, twisting and spitting. He recommended boating, jumping, swinging, wagon riding, and other exercises to fire up the internal organs.

The most important means of physical training of Avitsenna were bathing, bathing in cold water, drinking water and drinks, eating, sleeping and resting. He also showed the basics of fitness in old age and the transition to the seasons while traveling in general.

An in-depth study of the scientific and pedagogical teachings of Avitsenna in the field of physical education, as well as ways to apply them to people, taking into account their age, gender and social life, does not lose its relevance today. To do this, it is necessary to widely promote physical culture among the population, to convey to everyone the essence of its significance in strengthening human health and achieving physical maturity. Avitsennas experiments on the use of exercise to prevent and treat various diseases have received the approval of researchers and medical professionals around the world.

The great poet-humanist, like other great people of the medieval Renaissance, showed what a real person should be like throughout his life. He fought against the injustice of his time and expressed this in his works. Probably for this reason, the fact that the poet was a personal example, in turn, led to the appearance in his works of a unique interpretation of the ideas of humanity and goodness.

Amir Temur (1336-1405) - a major statesman and politician, founder of a large centralized state, commander. The activity of Sahibkiran Amir Temur is of great historical importance for the development of the Turan state and the development of culture. In the former Soviet era, the positive qualities and actions of Amir Temur were not mentioned or falsified, on the contrary, he was characterized as a spy, invader, colonialist. However, in large countries such as France, Great Britain and Germany, the positive qualities of Amir Temur are described on the basis of historical evidence.

There are separate chapters in Temur's Charters devoted to the issues of combat and physical training of troops and infantry, including infantry and equestrian combat, fencing and javelin throwing, combat and physical training of a warrior, high mountain regions, teeth, river crossing, etc. are described in detail. The process of walking, riding and fighting in those days was very difficult, requiring dexterity, speed, vigilance. When the time came, it took a lot of practical strength, dexterity, skill and courage to fight one on one with the enemy and defeat him.

Amir Temur himself taught many exercises to his emirs, ministers, commanders, centurions, captains and soldiers, taught students. He used swords, spears, bows, clubs, whips, ropes, and so on. All soldiers had to be fluent in these weapons. Each warrior was strong, agile, brave and a sniper. The fighters also used one-on-one riding, arguing, and overthrowing. These actions were also taught by Amir Temur and his special commanders.

Amir Temur spent his holidays hunting, hiking and camping. In such cases, he invented ways to climb mountains on horseback and on foot, using ropes and sticks. During his holidays, he encouraged the warriors to participate in activities such as horse racing, wrestling, fencing, and kupkari. Ladders, ropes and rappels were widely used to capture the city's forts. In his historical novel "Amir Temur" B. Akhmedov wrote about campaigns and battles in the mountains: Therefore, some slipped and fell on ropes, ladders and ropes. Hazrat Sahibkiran climbed the stairs, using a ladder of one hundred and fifty gases specially made for him ... The next day, before the sun had set, they climbed another mountain peak. So another two days went by." When crossing rivers, they used swimming, steering boats, and sailing over large areas using air-filled nets to cross fast and large rivers. Amir Temur knew how to find the right way to the destination, use the sun, moon and stars on the way. The use of military exercises was one of the priority areas of Amir Temur's activity.

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